

D2.3 – Europe Guideline for D&D Operation

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Abstract: This document outlines the challenges encountered during Dismantling & Decommissioning operation and demonstrates how the CLEANDEM solution could address some of these issues.

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Glossary

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
AMGA	Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement	INFN	<i>Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare</i>
AR	Augmented Reality	IoT	Internet of Things
BIM	Building Information Modelling	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
CA	Consortium Agreement	JRC	Joint Research Centre
CONOPS	Concept of Operations	JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf	M2M	Machine-to-Machine
CPO	CLEANDEM Project Office	MDA	Minimum Detectable Activity
D&D	Decommissioning and Dismantling / Decontamination and Decommissioning	NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency (part of OECD)
DoA	Description of Action	NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
DPC	Data Protection Correspondent	OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
DPO	Data Protection Officer	OGW	Out Gas Waste
DT	Digital Twin	PO	Project Officer/Office
EB	Executive Board	POPD	Protection Of Personal Data
EC	European Commission	PSD	Pulse Shape Discrimination
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable/Re-producible	Q&A	Questions and Answers
GA	General Assembly	RGB	Red, Green, Blue
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	RN	RadioNuclide
GrA	Grant Agreement	ROS	Robot Operating System
HMI	Human-Machine Interface	SiPM	Silicon PhotoMultiplier
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency	SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit	UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
		UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
		VR	Virtual Reality
		WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Nuclear dismantling is distinguished from civil deconstruction mainly by the presence of radioactivity and its colossal impact (costs, planning, safety, security, waste management, etc.) in the organization of worksites; an error in the original estimate or at a crucial stage of operations that could have major consequences for both safety (overexposure, significant events, etc.) and economic aspects.

This document gives an overview of the significant challenges inherent in the decommissioning and dismantling (D&D) of nuclear facilities and presents the CLEANDEM project as an innovative and realistic solution to these challenges based on concrete needs from end-users from nuclear industry. The CLEANDEM project, funded by the EU and gathering ten leading actors from Italy, Spain, France, and Germany aims to facilitate D&D operations through the development of a mobile unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) equipped with a robotic arm and advanced detection technologies for precise, 3D-localized radiological measurements. This initiative seeks to enhance safety, efficiency, and traceability in D&D operations by integrating innovative technologies and fostering collaboration among leading entities in the nuclear industry and research sectors across Europe.

Key Challenges in D&D Operations:

- **Radiological Safety and Waste Management:** Managing radiological hazards and the safe disposal of radioactive waste are paramount, necessitating advanced radiological assessments and waste management strategies to minimize risks to public health and the environment.
- **Operational Complexity:** The intricate nature of nuclear facilities demands meticulous planning and specialized expertise, highlighting the need for advanced technological solutions to navigate the complexities of D&D operations.
- **Regulatory and Compliance Obligations:** Adherence to stringent regulatory frameworks and effective stakeholder engagement are critical for ensuring safety, environmental protection, and public trust throughout the decommissioning process.

Innovations introduced by CLEANDEM :

- **Advanced Sensing and Robotic Systems:** The CLEANDEM project emphasizes the use of UGVs armed for remote and autonomous operations with sophisticated sensing technologies to automate and enhance the accuracy of radiological measurements, significantly reducing human exposure to radiation.
- **Digital Twin Technology:** The CLEANDEM solution offers a comprehensive 3D digital twin of the surveyed area, enhanced with detailed radiological data from various sensors. This also facilitates efficient planning and execution of dismantling activities while optimizing the sorting of nuclear waste for reprocessing or final storage. The digital twin not only provides a clear and detailed visualization of the scenario being examined but also evolves alongside the decommissioning operations. It serves as a dynamic record of the site's history, proving to be an invaluable tool for ongoing monitoring.
- **Improved Data Management and Traceability:** Through digitalization and the integration of advanced data management systems, the CLEANDEM project aims to improve the traceability and efficiency of D&D processes, facilitating better decision-making and project oversight.

Case Studies and Applications:

The document includes, as an example from SOGIN, their current approach for site and plant characterization. This example illustrates the potential of the CLEANDEM solutions to address specific operational challenges, from reducing human exposure to radiation, to improving the accuracy of radiological mapping.

Conclusion and Future Directions:

The CLEANDEM project stands as a significant advancement towards safer, more efficient, and cost-effective D&D operations. By addressing the numerous challenges of nuclear decommissioning with innovative technological solutions, CLEANDEM has the ambition to show a new standard in the field. Future developments will focus on enhancing the modularity and industrial applicability of the platform, ensuring that the innovations made in the project can be replicated and scaled according to industry needs.

Purpose of the document

The document details the challenges faced during dismantling operations and illustrates how the CLEANDEM project could provide solutions to overcome some of these difficulties.

1 Introduction

The dismantling and decommissioning of nuclear facilities represent crucial yet technically demanding phases in their lifecycle, requiring sophisticated solutions to address the complex challenges involved. These operations span a broad spectrum of radiological conditions, from the initial stages to the final steps where radioactivity has been significantly mitigated. Amidst this complexity, the CLEANDEM project emerges as a pioneering initiative aimed at improving the D&D process.

Funded by the EU and led by CEA LIST, the three-year CLEANDEM project aspires to create a groundbreaking platform to aid end-users throughout the D&D journey —from initial radiological assessment to the ultimate facility characterization, facilitating continuous monitoring. This endeavor is supported by a consortium of ten leading entities from the nuclear industry and research sectors across four European countries (France, Italy, Spain, and Germany). Together, they have developed a mobile unmanned ground vehicle (UGV), armed with advanced, highly mature detection technologies for precise 3D-localized radiological measurements. This innovation will enrich the existing facility data with a comprehensive and detailed digital twin of the surveyed area, significantly facilitating the planning and traceability of D&D operations.

By focusing on the technical hurdles within the D&D process and incorporating the CLEANDEM project's objectives, this document aims to underscore the importance of technological advancements and collaborative efforts in improving safety, and efficiency in nuclear decommissioning. Through exploring the latest in unmanned ground technology and digital twin modeling, CLEANDEM highlights the path forward in overcoming the technical challenges faced in nuclear facility decommissioning for safer and more efficient D&D operations.

2 Challenges in D&D Operation

According to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA): *“The main objectives of decommissioning are to place nuclear facilities that have reached the end of their useful lives in such a condition that they pose no unacceptable risks to the public, to workers or to the environment, and to reuse facilities and sites for new purposes,”* (IAEA, 2011). Achieving this necessitates reducing the levels of radioactivity in materials and facilities on-site to allow for their safe recycling, reuse, or categorization as either exempt or radioactive waste.

The challenge of D&D operations in the nuclear industry is intricate, requiring significant investment in both time and financial resources. The presence of radioactivity necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of dismantling processes and has a substantial impact on the costs involved.

For instance, irradiation levels can restrict operational times or render some activities unfeasible. In environments where contamination is present, extensive measures are essential to ensure the safety of operators. Additionally, the majority of waste generated during the dismantling process cannot be disposed of in the environment, recycled, or simply left on-site as might be the case in non-nuclear deconstruction scenarios.

A critical aspect of D&D operations is the management of nuclear waste. Depending on its classification, waste may require specific treatment or storage solutions. These processes represent significant cost factors and must be optimized to avoid unnecessary expenditures. It is crucial to identify the location, characterization, and radioactivity levels of waste early on, as well as to plan for its treatment, transportation, or storage, to overcome the complexities of D&D operations effectively.

2.1 Overview of Dismantling Operations

Dismantling operations in the decommissioning of nuclear facilities are intricate processes aimed at safely breaking down and removing all structures, systems, and components of a nuclear installation that has reached the end of its operational life. This process is crucial for eliminating potential hazards and preparing the site for potential future uses, ensuring no unacceptable risks are posed to the public, workers, or the environment. The operations are broadly categorized into several key phases, each with its unique challenges and requirements.

Before Dismantling

The preliminary phase encompasses all preparatory actions prior to commencing dismantling operations. This includes, but is not limited to, the development of detailed schedules, the collection of historical data, and thorough investigations to ascertain the initial radiological state and the physical inventory of the premises slated for dismantlement. This stage is foundational, ensuring a deep understanding of the site conditions and scope of work, thereby facilitating the precise definition of objectives across various optimization criteria (cost, schedule, safety, environmental impact, etc.). It is imperative to evaluate the reliability of these data critically, as their accuracy might be compromised due to unforeseen circumstances such as accidents, introduction of new radioactive materials, or human errors. In cases where critical information is lacking, further investigative efforts (radiological, chemical, physical) may be required to ensure a good understanding of the situation before proceeding with decommissioning.

In Progress

This phase marks the active execution of decommissioning operations. Activities during this stage include decontamination, dismantling, and the removal of components, systems, or structures within the designated area, as well as the remediation of any residual contamination on walls and floors. Should civil engineering structures be involved, it necessitates the thorough decontamination of the ground to remove any trace of contamination alongside the disposal of both radioactive and non-radioactive waste. Radiological measurements are conducted at various stages to monitor the evolving situation, aiding in the management and decision-making processes for subsequent on-site actions. This phase also involves radiological characterization to facilitate the planning of the remediation phase, with an emphasis on assessing the radioactivity levels of waste to optimize sorting and disposal strategies.

After Dismantling

The final phase of D&D operations starts once all remediation efforts are complete, and the facility has achieved the desired end state. This signifies that the area has been entirely cleared of radioactive materials and is ready for release or repurposing. An essential component of this stage is the rigorous evaluation of residual activity to ensure the absence of radioactivity. Given the requirement for very low Minimum Detectable Activities (MDAs), the reliance on in-situ measurements decreases in favor of laboratory analyses, which can detect lower levels of radioactivity. Despite the potential for extensive areas requiring examination—sometimes exceeding hundreds of thousands of square meters—this evaluation is crucial to confirm the site's suitability for its next intended use.

2.2 Environmental Challenges

The Decommissioning and Dismantling of nuclear facilities present a myriad of environmental challenges, underscored by the imperative to manage and dispose of radioactive waste safely. These materials, by their nature, pose long-term hazards to human health and the environment, necessitating meticulous strategies to mitigate their impact. The overarching goal of D&D operations is not only to dismantle the physical structures but also to address the residual contamination of soil and groundwater, manage hazardous materials, and ultimately, restore the site for future use.

Radioactive Waste Management

One of the most significant environmental challenges in D&D operations is the safe handling, treatment, and disposal of radioactive waste. This waste varies widely in terms of its radioactivity level, ranging from low-level waste, such as contaminated tools and clothing, to high-level waste, like used nuclear fuel. Each category requires specific disposal strategies to prevent environmental contamination. The process involves sophisticated waste characterization, segregation, and containment measures to ensure that radioactive materials do not pose a risk to the ecosystem and public health.

Soil and Groundwater Contamination

Nuclear facilities, especially those with a lengthy operational history, may have contributed to the contamination of soil and groundwater with radioactive substances. Addressing this issue involves comprehensive environmental monitoring and remediation techniques to identify the extent of contamination and effectively decontaminate affected areas. Remediation strategies might include soil excavation, in-situ treatment, and the containment of contaminated groundwater to prevent further spread.

Restoration and Site Reuse

Beyond the removal of contaminants and radioactive materials, environmental challenges extend to restoring the site to a condition that is safe for reuse, whether for industrial, commercial, or public purposes. This requires detailed environmental impact assessments to guide the restoration process, ensuring that the site meets all regulatory requirements for environmental protection. Restoration efforts may involve soil replacement, revegetation, and the establishment of natural habitats to promote ecological recovery.

Mitigating Environmental Impact

Effective mitigation of environmental impacts necessitates an approach, integrating advanced technologies and practices throughout the D&D process. This includes employing minimally invasive techniques for dismantling and decontamination to reduce the disturbance to the site and surrounding areas. Additionally, the adoption of sustainable waste management practices, such as waste minimization, recycling, and the conversion of waste to energy, plays a crucial role in reducing the environmental footprint of D&D operations.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive, scientifically informed approach that prioritizes safety, environmental protection, and sustainability. Through meticulous planning, innovative technologies, and adherence to stringent regulatory standards, it is possible to mitigate the environmental impacts of D&D operations, ensuring a safe and sustainable legacy for future generations.

2.3 Technical and Operational Challenges

D&D operations of nuclear facilities entail a series of technical and operational challenges. These challenges demand meticulous planning, specialized expertise, and the implementation of advanced technologies to guarantee the safety, efficiency, and effectiveness of the entire process. Below is a detailed exploration of these challenges.

Radiological Safety

One of the primary technical challenges in D&D operations involves managing the radiological hazards inherent to nuclear facilities. Ensuring the safety of workers and the surrounding environment requires a clear understanding of radiological assessments, effective decontamination procedures, and stringent control measures. Advanced radiological monitoring and mapping technologies are essential for accurately assessing contamination levels and guiding decontamination efforts.

Complexity of Structures

Nuclear facilities are characterized by their complex infrastructures and specialized equipment. The dismantling of these structures poses significant technical challenges, requiring detailed engineering analyses and the development of customized dismantling strategies. Operations must be meticulously planned to manage the risks associated with the structural integrity of buildings and containment systems during dismantlement.

Waste Management

The classification, treatment, and disposal of radioactive waste are critical components of D&D operations, presenting both technical and operational challenges. Determining the most appropriate disposal route for different waste types involves complex decision-making processes, governed by regulatory requirements and environmental considerations. The need for specialized facilities for waste treatment and disposal further complicates waste management efforts.

Technological Requirements

D&D operations rely heavily on technological solutions to address the different challenges they present. The use of remote handling and robotic technologies is increasingly common, particularly for tasks that pose high radiation risks to workers. However, developing and deploying these technologies require significant investment and expertise. Moreover, the adaptation of existing technologies to the unique conditions of each decommissioning project adds a layer of complexity.

The technical and operational challenges of Decommissioning and Dismantling nuclear facilities are diverse and complex. Addressing these challenges requires an approach that combines technical expertise, advanced technologies, strategic planning, and rigorous regulatory compliance.

2.4 Regulatory, Compliance Challenges and Stakeholder Engagement

D&D operations are not only technical but also exercises in meticulous regulatory compliance and stakeholder engagement. Governed by an intricate web of national and international regulations, D&D processes are designed to ensure the highest standards of safety, environmental protection, and waste management. This section underscores the necessity of an approach that balances technical precision with regulatory diligence and community involvement, setting the stage for a comprehensive discussion on the challenges and strategies that define successful decommissioning projects.

Regulatory Framework and Compliance Challenges in D&D Operations

Decommissioning of nuclear facilities is governed by a stringent regulatory framework that mandates adherence to high safety, environmental, and waste management standards. This regulatory landscape presents a formidable challenge, necessitating meticulous planning and ongoing dialogue with regulatory bodies to ensure comprehensive compliance. Regulatory bodies impose these mandates to safeguard public and environmental health, marking the decommissioning process with rigorous oversight.

The establishment of a decommissioning strategy is pivotal, shaped by the prevailing regulatory policies which, although varying from one country to another, universally demand a structured framework of laws and regulations. This framework outlines the responsibilities of governments, regulatory authorities (covering nuclear safety, public health, industrial safety, etc.), licensees, owners, and decommissioning operators. It encompasses key parliamentary acts, departmental decrees, and guidelines essential for developing a decommissioning programme within the stipulated legal and regulatory confines.

A crucial aspect of this framework is the classification of waste, determining whether it is radioactive or not, based on the regulatory definitions provided by authorities. This determination guides the project's approach to radiological investigations and characterization, ensuring that waste is managed and disposed of appropriately. To navigate these regulatory requirements, projects often refer to documents and checklists, such as those provided by the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (OECD, 2003) which include acts, relevant departmental ordinances/decrees and regulator's decrees and guidance relevant to decommissioning. Those concern:

- Decommissioning licensing,
- Decommissioning operation,
- Site release after decommissioning,
- Radiation protection, public health, health, and safety,
- Material clearance, reusable material, and waste management,
- Environmental protection, and environmental impact assessment,
- Industrial safety, and fire protection,
- Civil construction,
- Area and landscape development, nature, and heritage protection...

Stakeholder Engagement and Public Trust

Alongside regulatory compliance, engaging with stakeholders is central to the D&D process. Effective communication and collaboration with local communities, government entities, and environmental organizations are essential for addressing concerns, ensuring transparency, and building trust. This engagement is not just a regulatory requirement but a strategic imperative that influences the success of decommissioning projects. Addressing and integrating stakeholder feedback into the decommissioning strategy enhances public acceptance and supports the project's social license to operate.

Navigating the complex regulatory environment, coupled with the imperative to foster positive stakeholder relations, demands a proactive, informed, and transparent approach. By adhering to these principles, decommissioning projects can achieve their safety, environmental, and societal objectives, laying the groundwork for the responsible closure of nuclear sites.

2.5 Economic and Financial Challenges

The decommissioning and dismantling of nuclear facilities represent a significant financial undertaking, marked by a range of economic and financial challenges. These challenges arise from

the inherent complexities of the D&D process, the need for stringent safety and environmental measures, and the long-term nature of many decommissioning projects. Understanding these economic and financial hurdles is essential for the planning and successful execution of D&D operations.

Cost Estimation and Management

One of the foremost challenges in D&D operations is the accurate estimation and management of costs. Decommissioning projects are inherently complex and can span several decades, making initial cost predictions difficult and often subject to significant revisions. Factors such as unexpected contamination levels, changes in regulatory requirements, and technological advancements can dramatically alter project timelines and expenses. Effective cost management strategies, including contingency planning and dynamic financial modeling, are crucial to mitigate these uncertainties.

Funding and Financing

Securing sufficient funding is another critical challenge. The substantial upfront investment required for D&D activities often exceeds the financial capabilities of the facility's operators or owners. Moreover, the long duration of decommissioning projects complicates the allocation and management of funds over time. Developing sustainable financing mechanisms, such as decommissioning funds or reserve accounts, and exploring public-private partnerships can provide viable solutions to these funding challenges.

Waste Management and Disposal Costs

The treatment, storage, and disposal of radioactive waste generated during D&D operations entail substantial costs. The financial implications of waste management are influenced by the volume and classification of waste, the availability of disposal facilities, and the stringent regulatory standards governing waste processing and disposal. Developing cost-effective waste management strategies, including waste minimization and recycling where feasible, is essential to controlling overall project costs.

Market Fluctuations and Regulatory Changes

Economic and financial planning for D&D operations must also account for market fluctuations and potential regulatory changes. The costs of labor, materials, and waste disposal can vary significantly over time, impacting project budgets. Similarly, changes in regulatory frameworks can introduce new financial burdens, necessitating agile financial planning and risk management approaches.

Economic Impact and Job Transition

The economic impact of D&D operations extends beyond the immediate financial considerations of the project. The closure of nuclear facilities can have significant implications for local economies, particularly in regions where the facility is a major employer. Managing the transition for workers and the community, including retraining and job placement programs, is an important aspect of mitigating the economic fallout. Additionally, revitalizing decommissioned sites for new industrial or commercial uses can offer economic opportunities post-decommissioning.

The economic and financial challenges of decommissioning and dismantling operations are numerous, requiring careful planning, robust financial management, and proactive stakeholder

engagement. Addressing these challenges effectively is key to ensuring the financial viability of D&D projects, mitigating economic impacts on communities, and achieving the overarching goals of safety, environmental protection, and site restoration.

Given the breadth of environmental, technical, regulatory, economic, and societal challenges inherent in decommissioning and dismantling operations, the path forward necessitates a pivot towards innovative solutions. These solutions not only promise to address the complexities and uncertainties of D&D projects but also to redefine the processes, making them safer, more efficient, and economically viable.

3 Comprehensive Innovations in D&D Operations

Innovation aimed at enhancing D&D operations is a dynamic field where technology, methodology, and collaboration converge to address challenges inherent in these processes. These innovations not only aim to increase the safety, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of D&D projects but also strive to mitigate environmental impact and ensure regulatory compliance.

This chapter highlights standard operating procedures that underpin D&D activities, the rationale driving change within these operations, the broad spectrum of identified innovation axes, and the specific innovations introduced by the CLEANDEM project.

3.1 Standard Operating Procedures for D&D Activities

D&D activities require meticulous planning and execution. The foundation of successful D&D operations lies in the detailed documentation of operating procedures. These documents serve as comprehensive guides, outlining every aspect of the project from initiation to completion. The critical components of such procedures include:

Initial Assessment and Planning

- Initial state description: a thorough analysis of the facility's current condition, including structural integrity, radiological status, and any hazardous materials present.
- Dismantling stages definition: a step-by-step breakdown of the dismantling process, categorizing the sequence of operations to ensure systematic progress.
- Schedule and duration: an outline of the anticipated timeline for the project, detailing the start and end dates of each stage and the overall duration of the D&D operation.

Operational Planning

- Work description: a detailed description of the tasks to be undertaken, specifying the methodologies and technologies to be employed.
- Equipment and process identification: identification of any new equipment needed for the project, along with descriptions of the associated processes and their integration into the operation.
- Safety and radioprotection: establishment of safety objectives and procedures, including risk assessments, dosimetry, and the requisite personal protective equipment, to safeguard all personnel involved.
- Environmental protection: strategies and methodologies aimed at minimizing environmental impact, addressing soil and water protection, air quality, and other relevant environmental concerns.

Waste Management and Remediation

- Waste quantities estimate: an estimate of the types and volumes of waste expected, facilitating planning for waste handling, treatment, and disposal.
- Waste management strategy: a comprehensive approach to managing the inventory of waste materials, including solid and liquid effluents, atmospheric discharges, and the protocols for waste sorting and disposal.

- Remediation methodologies: detailed descriptions of the remediation techniques selected for soil and structural decontamination, ensuring the site meets all regulatory requirements for environmental restoration.

Execution and Oversight

- Dismantling operation management: a framework for the oversight and management of dismantling operations, ensuring adherence to planned procedures, schedules, and safety protocols.

By adhering to these operating procedures, D&D projects can achieve their objectives efficiently and safely, minimizing risks to personnel, the public, and the environment. Such comprehensive documentation not only facilitates the execution of tasks but also guarantee regulatory compliance and supports transparent communication with all stakeholders involved.

3.2 Rationale for Change in Decommissioning and Dismantling Operations

The imperative for change in Decommissioning and Dismantling (D&D) projects stems from the persistent challenges encountered throughout the different processes described before in this document. This paragraph gives an overview of the main issues encountered during D&D operations.

Historical Data Collection Challenges

The initial phase of dismantling activities involves the collection of historical data. This critical step compiles all relevant information from previous interventions and any pertinent details necessary for the upcoming dismantling process. Common hurdles in managing these data include:

- Incomplete datasets, leading to gaps in information.
- Unreliability of existing data, questioning its accuracy.
- Incident reports lacking in detail, providing insufficient insight into past occurrences.
- Loss of information due to the departure or retirement of key personnel, resulting in a lack of traceability.
- Documentation on the evolution of facilities is often inadequate or inaccurately reported, complicating the understanding of "as-constructed" versus "as-existing" states.

In scenarios where information is significantly lacking, establishing a new baseline becomes essential to redefine the initial state accurately.

Radiological and Topographical Mapping Challenges

Radiological and topographical mapping is fundamental for preparing precise maps and identifying radioactive elements within a site, significantly impacting the project's efficiency and scope. Challenges in this domain include:

- Measurement quality: difficulties arise from restricted access to areas, cluttered environments, or insufficient lighting, leading to incomplete data collection.
- Traceability: issues with reporting and archiving measurements, coupled with the time-intensive nature of data analysis, can hinder process efficiency.
- Human and organizational factors: misinterpretations, data entry errors, and oversights contribute to inaccuracies and mismanagement.

- Extremes in radiation levels: special attention is needed for areas with very high or low levels of radioactivity, which pose unique challenges in data retrieval and equipment functionality.

Operational Challenges

The execution of D&D operations encounters several obstacles, often unique to each project but typically revolving around:

- Access constraints: ensuring physical and radiological access to conduct measurements or interventions can be challenging due to safety measures or physical barriers.
- Resource availability: the necessity for adequate financial and human resources to support the extensive scope of operations.
- Management of contingencies: unforeseen events and hazards inherent to on-site realities necessitate robust contingency planning.

Waste Management-Related Problems

Issues in waste management frequently intersect with dismantling challenges, including:

- Inefficient waste sorting practices, affecting waste processing and disposal.
- Loss of historical waste information, complicating waste categorization.
- Underestimation or overestimation of waste activity levels, impacting economic planning.
- Combined chemical, radiological, and occasionally, biological risks that complicate waste handling procedures.

By addressing these diverse challenges there is an opportunity to significantly refine the approach to D&D operations, enhancing safety, efficiency, and environmental stewardship.

3.3 Axes of Innovation

The axes of innovation for D&D operations focus on different areas to improve safety, efficiency, and environmental sustainability. Key axes of innovation are described below.

Data Management and Digitalization

Digital technologies, including data management systems, modeling, and simulation tools, can enhance planning, decision-making, and collaboration in D&D operations. These technologies facilitate efficient data collection, analysis, and sharing, improving project management, safety assessments, and regulatory compliance.

Robotics and Remote Systems

Robotics plays a crucial role in D&D operations by enabling remote handling of radioactive materials and performing tasks in hazardous environments. Advances in robotics technology, including teleoperated and autonomous systems, can enhance safety, precision, and efficiency in dismantling, decontamination, and waste management processes.

Characterization and Imaging Techniques

Innovative techniques for characterizing and imaging radioactivity are essential for accurate assessment and planning of D&D activities. This includes advancements in radiation detection, spectroscopy, imaging systems, and non-destructive testing methods to identify, locate, and quantify radioactive and hazardous materials.

Advanced Decontamination Technologies

Developing efficient and effective decontamination methods is crucial for reducing the volume and hazard level of radioactive waste generated during D&D. Innovations in chemical, mechanical, and biological decontamination techniques can enhance the decontamination process, minimizing waste generation and reducing costs.

Waste Management and Disposal Technologies

Innovative approaches to radioactive waste management, such as advanced treatment and disposal technologies, can optimize waste packaging, transportation, and final disposal. This includes techniques for volume reduction, encapsulation, immobilization, and long-term storage solutions to ensure safe and environmentally sound waste management.

Materials recycling and reuse innovations can help minimize waste generation and reduce the need for raw materials during D&D. Technologies for segregating, processing, and recycling materials from decommissioned facilities can contribute to resource conservation and economic sustainability.

Stakeholder Engagement and Social Innovation

Innovations in stakeholder engagement processes and social innovation can foster transparent communication, public participation, and the integration of local communities' needs and concerns into the D&D process. This includes participatory decision-making approaches, public education initiatives, and socioeconomic revitalization strategies for post-D&D site reuse.

By focusing on these axes of innovation, stakeholders in the nuclear industry can address the needs of D&D more effectively, ensuring safer, more efficient, and sustainable decommissioning and decontamination of nuclear facilities.

3.4 Areas of Innovation covered by the CLEANDEM Project

The CLEANDEM project, which will be described in detail in the next chapter, represents a significant stride toward innovating decommissioning and dismantling (D&D) operations, focusing on three critical areas: improved measurement, enhanced intervention, and advanced data management. By addressing these key aspects, CLEANDEM aims to solve prevalent challenges in D&D projects.

Improved Measurement Techniques

At the heart of CLEANDEM's innovation is the substantial enhancement of measurement processes, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of data collected during D&D operations. The project introduces a different approach to measurement improvements:

- Enhanced quality and quantity of information: incorporating advanced measurement technologies, including energy spectra for effective radiological identification in challenging zones, and low-cost sensors for rapid dose rate mapping. Neutron measurements distinguish between gamma and neutron contributions, while contamination monitoring tools detect low levels of alpha and beta activities on diverse surfaces, even in significant background radiation.
- Precise spatial location: every measurement is associated with spatial coordinates (x, y, z), enabling precise mapping and identification of contamination hotspots. The integration of a lightweight gamma camera facilitates 2D irradiation mapping, providing critical data for accurate dose rate estimations.
- 3D environmental reconstruction: utilizing 3D scanning technologies, CLEANDEM achieves complete environmental reconstructions, offering a comprehensive visual and data-driven understanding of the facility's condition.

Enhanced Intervention Strategies

The project capitalizes on the use of Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs) to improve intervention approaches in D&D activities:

- Mitigating radiological risks: the UGV platform, equipped with necessary probes and a robotic arm significantly reduces human exposure to radiation.
- Repetitive and accurate task execution: configured for consistency, the UGV ensures reliable data collection under varying operational conditions. This robotic solution streamlines interventions, making them more efficient and reducing human error.

Advanced Data Management Capabilities

CLEANDEM's approach to data management leverages digital technologies to enhance the utility and accessibility of information gathered during D&D operations:

- Digital twin integration: by merging historical data (when available) with data from the UGV, CLEANDEM creates a digital twin of the facility, significantly improving planning and execution strategies. This digitalization effort aims to mitigate issues related to data loss and historical record archiving.
- Complete traceability and enhanced user experience: implementing a system of complete traceability ensures that all data, including measurements, spatial coordinates, and relevant annotations, are systematically recorded and easily accessible. Visualization of these data on a 3D model not only enhances the accuracy of interventions but also improves the overall user experience.

Through these innovative measures, the CLEANDEM project is setting new standards in the field of D&D operations. By addressing measurement accuracy, intervention safety, and data management efficiency, CLEANDEM proposes a new way for safer, more efficient, and environmentally responsible decommissioning practices.

After outlining the spectrum of innovations in D&D operations, from the foundation of standard operating procedures through to the innovations introduced by the CLEANDEM project, a precise examination the solution will be presented in the next chapter including the project's goals, methodologies, and its potential to significantly influence D&D operations, showcasing CLEANDEM's role in setting new benchmarks in the field.

4 The CLEANDEM Project

4.1 Presentation of the Project

The **CLEANDEM** (Michel, 2023) acronym stands for **Cyber physicalL Equipment for unmAnned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements**. Funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme, the CLEANDEM project aims to develop an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) platform equipped with advanced radiological sensing probes. These tools are designed to facilitate the entire spectrum of D&D operations, from the initial radiological assessment to the final characterization of nuclear facilities.

Since its inception in March 2021, the CLEANDEM consortium presented in Figure 1 has united leading experts from the European nuclear industry (including CAEN, ORANO, ANSALDO, RINA, TECNALIA, SOGIN, AiNT) and the research sector (CEA, INFN, ENEA). This collaboration seeks to overcome a critical challenge in D&D operations: reducing radiation exposure to human operators throughout various stages of the process.

Figure 1: The CLEANDEM project gathers ten leading actors from Italy, Spain, France, and Germany.

To this end, the CLEANDEM partners have carefully selected a set of proven sensors that exhibit technological maturity levels ranging from TRL 5 (partial-scale prototype validation) to TRL 7 (full-scale prototype in commercial conditions), aligning with specific D&D requirements. These readiness levels indicate that the sensors are primed for integration into key scenarios with minimal additional engineering, streamlining their adoption for practical use.

4.2 Challenges and Methodology

CLEANDEM addresses numerous challenges to enhance Decommissioning and Dismantling operations across various dimensions:

- **Radiation safety:** reducing the radiation exposure for operators involved in D&D activities to ensure their safety and well-being.
- **Efficiency and cost-effectiveness:** streamlining D&D operations to minimize both the time and financial resources required, achieving more cost-efficient outcomes.
- **Traceability enhancement:** enhancing the traceability of D&D processes to ensure comprehensive documentation and accountability throughout the operations.
- **Operational versatility:** demonstrating the capability of the platform to effectively function across all phases of D&D operations, showcasing its adaptability and reliability.
- **Data collection and analysis:** facilitating faster and more precise data collection methods to simplify and expedite the clean-up process, thereby improving overall project efficiency.

The methodology adopted for the advancement and application of technologies within the CLEANDEM project unfolds in three distinct phases, each aimed at refining the tools and processes for D&D operations:

Phase 1: Preparation and Planning

This initial phase lays the groundwork for the project by meticulously identifying technical specifications and conducting a state-of-the-art assessment of the technologies incorporated into the CLEANDEM toolbox. This comprehensive evaluation ensures that the project builds on the latest advancements in the field. Additionally, this phase involves defining various scenarios that mirror the different stages of D&D operations, including the initial radiological status assessment, ongoing operations, and the final characterization of facilities. These scenarios are crucial for tailoring the development and application of CLEANDEM technologies to real-world D&D challenges.

Phase 2: Technology Development and Integration

The second phase focuses on the development and optimization of the selected technologies identified in Phase 1. This includes refining the functionalities and capabilities of the tools to meet the specific needs of D&D operations. A key aspect of this phase is the integration of these technologies with the UGV platform, enhancing its localization and navigation capabilities. Furthermore, this phase facilitates the transfer of recorded data to the Digital Twin (DT), a virtual replica of the physical facility, which plays a pivotal role in planning, monitoring, and executing D&D operations.

Phase 3: Evaluation and Performance Assessment

The final phase is dedicated to the thorough evaluation of the developed technologies and their integration with the UGV platform. This includes testing the combined system's effectiveness in real D&D measurement conditions, assessing both individual technologies and their synergy when deployed as part of the UGV platform. Performance assessment is critical to validating the efficacy,

reliability, and efficiency of the CLEANDEM project's solutions, ensuring they meet the rigorous demands of D&D operations.

By following this structured approach, the CLEANDEM project aims to deliver innovative and practical solutions that significantly enhance the safety, efficiency, and effectiveness of D&D operations, minimizing risks and maximizing outcomes.

4.3 Key technologies

The CLEANDEM project integrates an array of advanced sensors and technologies onto a platform to enhance the process of decommissioning and dismantling nuclear facilities. This ensemble of innovations encompasses:

Robotic Mobility and Manipulation (Figure 2, Figure 3)

The sensors' mobility is powered by Robotnik's RB-VOGUI, a robust platform designed for challenging environments. The dimensions of the platform are 104 cm × 65 cm × 56 cm. The addition of a Universal Robots' UR 5e robotic arm, contributed by TECNALIA and ANSALDO, respectively, provides precise manipulation capabilities, essential for intricate D&D tasks.

Figure 2: Robotnik's RB-VOGUI platform with the Universal Robots' UR 5e robotic arm.

Figure 3: Sensors on RB-VOGUI for navigation and localization of the platform.

Surface Contamination Detection

The platform features a pixelated β/γ surface contamination detector developed by CEA, enabling precise detection of beta and gamma radiation on surfaces. Additionally, a large area α/β surface contamination detector from CAEN enhances the platform's ability to monitor both alpha and beta radiation across extensive areas.

Pixelated Plastic Scintillator (CEA)

Figure 4 presents the system based on Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) of phoswich scintillators. It consists of 5 cm \times 5 cm plastic scintillators housed within a modular frame, designed for flexible assembly to conform to the contours of the surface being measured. Each scintillator is coupled with a Silicon Photomultiplier (SiPM) and readout electronics, all mounted on springs. This design enables the scintillators to adjust and maintain proximity to the surface, ensuring optimal performance even on irregular surfaces.

Figure 4: The pixelated detector developed by CEA.

Large Surface PSD Phoswich Contamination Monitor (CAEN)

Given the dual β/γ detection capability of the CEA system, this development was strategically redirected towards creating a system dedicated to α/β detection. This adjustment leverages the complementary strengths of both systems, allowing them to be integrated onto the robotic arm for a broader range of contaminant detection.

CAEN's phoswich contamination monitor, with its substantial surface area of 576 cm², is adept at α/β measurement. The device employs a 25 μm ZnS(Ag) coating for alpha detection, which is coupled with a PVT scintillator for beta detection. Both elements are connected to a light guide, directing the captured light to the photomultiplier. Considering the sensor's large area influences the light output and working in coincidence can further reduce the noise level, a specific geometry utilizing two photomultiplier tubes (PMT) positioned on opposite sides was selected to optimize detection efficiency. The monitor is visible on Figure 5.

Figure 5: CAEN's PSD phoswich detector on the robotic arm.

Imaging, Spectrometry, and Identification Sensors

For an enhanced radiological analysis, the compact gamma spectrometer from CAEN and the Nanopix3 miniaturized gamma spectro-imager from CEA are integral to the platform. The upgraded SNIPER-GN and GAMON, a collaborative effort between CAEN and INFN, further bolsters the platform with its advanced γ/n identification features.

Nanopix3 (CEA)

CEA's Nanopix3 stands as the world's most compact coded-aperture gamma spectro-imager, with dimensions of 12 cm × 7 cm × 5.4 cm. Weighing just 420 grams, it is light enough to be mounted on a robotic arm (as well as on an UAV, as shown in the H2020 project TERRIFIC), as shown in

Figure 6, enabling it to scan in any direction to pinpoint gamma radiation hotspots. Integrating a miniature RGB camera, Nanopix3 merges the visible spectrum imagery with post-processed data from a pixelated Timepix3 ASIC hybridized with a 1 mm-thick cadmium telluride semiconductor. This sophisticated fusion produces an overlaid image that combines both visual and radiological information, offering a comprehensive view of the radiation source.

Figure 6: On the left, the measurement of a ^{152}Eu source inside a metallic drum is shown with Nanopix3. The middle picture represents the location of a hot spot. On the right, the associated gamma energy spectrum is displayed.

CZT sensor (CAEN)

This system features a low-power, and highly energy-efficient detection mechanism, anchored by a CZT (Cadmium Zinc Telluride) detector (see Figure 7). The design incorporates a large-volume, hemispheric CZT detector, tailored for arm-mounted deployment (probe dimensions: Length × Diameter = 12 cm × 5 cm). This setup facilitates in-depth gamma analysis early in the survey. It is specially engineered to access and inspect locations that are challenging for bulkier sensors to reach.

Figure 7: Compact CZT sensor provided by CAEN.

SNIPER-GN (CAEN)

The Sniper GN presented in Figure 8, designed for gamma and neutron detection, integrates a 38 mm × 38 mm CeBr₃ crystal alongside a 51 mm × 51 mm stilbene scintillator. This system operates in two primary modes to enhance radiological assessments:

- Search or continuous mode: this mode facilitates ongoing surveillance of radiological levels of gamma and neutrons while the platform is in motion, continuously monitoring the environment.
- Identification (ID) mode: focused on pinpointing specific sources of gamma and neutron radiation, this mode activates when the device is stationary in front of a designated position. To accurately identify the sources, the platform remains fixed for approximately one minute, allowing for detailed analysis.

The SNIPER GN also includes additional features such as:

- Radioisotope identification: the system efficiently lists identified radioisotopes, providing crucial data and their outdoor locations when such information is available.
- Adjustable radiological thresholds: operators can customize radiological thresholds to set alarms, enabling tailored alert parameters based on specific safety requirements.
- Background measurement capability: this feature allows for the collection of background radiation measurements, offering a baseline against which to compare detected radiological levels.

Figure 8: The SNIPER GN system developed by CAEN.

GAMON (CAEN)

The NaI(Li) detector within the GAMON system (see Figure 9) is capable of performing both gamma spectrometry and neutron detection through PSD using a single device. While this approach offers the convenience of dual functionality, it does so at the expense of gamma energy resolution, which is inferior to that of the CeBr3 crystal. However, when paired with the Sniper GN system, this combination enhances gamma/neutron mapping capabilities. This synergy allows for the precise identification of radionuclides by analyzing the specific neutron to gamma ratio they present, thereby improving the overall accuracy and effectiveness of radiological assessments.

Figure 9 : The GAMON system developed by CAEN.

Radiation Counting

Incorporating low-cost, innovative solutions for radiation measurement, the MiniRadMeter and MiniSiLiF (developed by INFN) serve as gamma and neutron counters, respectively, offering cost-effective options for radiation monitoring. More details and results for both sensors are available in (Rossi, 2023).

MiniRadMeter (INFN)

MiniRadMeter is a miniature gamma counter and spectrometer presented in Figure 10. The scintillator chosen for gamma detection is a CsI(Tl), paired with a Silicon Photomultiplier (SiPM). This selection is grounded in the scintillator's superior detection attributes, including its high detection efficiency—attributable to its notable density—alongside very good light yield and energy resolution, all available at an economical cost.

Figure 10: On the left side, the MiniRadMeter (red circle) on the robotic platform. On the right side, an exploded 3D view of the sensor.

MiniSiLiF (INFN)

MiniSiLiF sensor is a miniature neutron counter presented in Figure 11. It incorporates a ${}^6\text{LiF}$ layer for converting slow neutrons, utilizing a moderator (a $6\text{ cm} \times 6\text{ cm} \times 6\text{ cm}$ polyethylene box) to decelerate them. This setup leverages the reaction ${}^6\text{Li} + n_{\text{slow}} \rightarrow {}^7\text{Li} \rightarrow \alpha + {}^3\text{H}$, where the resulting alpha or triton particles are detected by a silicon diode. Should the focus be solely on thermal neutrons, the moderator can be omitted, allowing the SiLiF detector to operate independently, thereby providing flexibility in neutron detection based on the specific requirements of the operation.

Figure 11: On the left side, the MiniSiLiF (red circle) on the robotic platform. On the right side, parts, and an exploded 3D view of the sensor.

Other innovative sensors

The CLEANDEM project also developed specialized sensors which will not be embedded into the robotic platform like a cryogenic system for $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ monitoring (ENEA) and fiber optics-coupled OSL dosimetry & shape-sensing technology (CEA). These sensors offer unique insights into the decommissioning environment, from carbon dioxide levels to detailed dosimetry data.

Cryogenic System for $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ monitoring (ENEA)

The proposed technology is based on cryogenic separation of CO_2 from air shown in Figure 12. It can be applied to selective monitoring of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ in air. With this apparatus, it is possible to determine the trapping efficiency of CO_2 from ambient air and continuously read $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ concentration in air. This solution combines an effective monitoring and a trapping efficiency close to 100%.

Figure 12: Cryogenic System for $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ monitoring developed by ENEA.

Fiber optics-coupled OSL dosimetry & shape-sensing technology (CEA)

This solution aims to acquire both topographic and radiological data in areas that are difficult to access or concealed. In this particular case, endoscopic techniques are proposed as substitute to SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) often used in open spaces. OSL/FO dosimeters presented in Figure 13, are compact enough to be inserted through available openings, and facilitate radiological assessments in these challenging zones. However, accurately pinpointing the location of these miniature detectors often relies on outdated or sometimes missing original blueprints, leading to potential inaccuracies.

To overcome this, shape sensing technology, already proven in medical fields for short distances (less than 1 meter), is being adapted for D&D purposes in the CLEANDEM project. This adaptation includes extending the technology's range for long-distance monitoring (up to 10 – 13 meters) and enhancing its durability under radiation exposure.

Fiber optic shape sensing leverages an optical fiber cable to map the 3D contour of an object in real-time, even without direct line of sight. This technique accurately determines the position and shape of any point along the cable in 3D space, based on the strain changes detected in multicore fibers or specially designed cables containing several single-mode fibers. By analyzing the strain profiles along each fiber core, an algorithm can reconstruct the cable's shape from the collected data. Within CLEANDEM, shape sensing employs a 7-core Multi-Core Fiber (MCF), with six fibers arranged around a central one, to provide essential topographic information for effective 3D reconstruction in D&D scenarios.

Figure 13: OSL/FO dosimeters developed by CEA.

Geolocalized dosimetric data are eventually used as input to a 3D activity reconstruction algorithm involving Monte-Carlo modeling. The 3D internal activity distribution may then be assessed inside hidden or out of reach zones (inside reactor, pipes, etc.) thanks to endoscopic techniques (OSL/FO coupled to shape sensing).

Digital Twin Integration

Central to the CLEANDEM project is the Digital Twin, powered by RINA's Qpro² software and augmented with PoStLAM, a software tailored for radiological analysis developed by ORANO. This digital replication of the physical environment not only aids in planning and executing D&D operations but also serves as a dynamic repository of all collected data, enabling updates and decision-making support.

Qpro² Software (RINA)

The Qpro² multiplatform, a web-based application, plays a pivotal role in developing the digital twin by integrating data from the diverse sensors discussed earlier in this document. This DT effectively visualizes in 3D all relevant information for D&D operations, collating inputs from a variety of sources, including sensors, material samples, and pre-existing databases, as shown in Figure 14 where the architecture of the software is presented. The DT is designed to present this comprehensive data set via an interactive dashboard and a detailed 3D model of the facility, enhancing the user's understanding and interaction with the information. Furthermore, it is geared towards identifying and displaying key indicators and conducting thorough analyses of historical data, thereby offering a robust tool for comprehensive data analysis and visualization in D&D projects.

A key feature is its capability to assist in making informed D&D decisions, guiding the strategy and planning of scenarios.

Figure 14: Architecture of the QPRO² software.

PoStLAM (ORANO)

PoStLAM is a versatile software designed for 3D analysis, capable of processing and integrating topographical and radiological data through two main data types:

- **Topographical Data:** This includes data such as point clouds, which can be obtained through photogrammetry, structured light projection, or 3D scanners, providing detailed surface mapping.
- **Radiological Data:** These are measurements that are precisely positioned within a space, collected manually, with static sensors, or through robotic means, offering critical safety information.

PoStLAM operates in two distinct modes, catering to different user needs:

- **Viewer PoStLAM - Enhanced 3D Environment:**
 - Offers the ability to visualize 3D scans alongside positioned measurements like dose rates and gamma spectra.
 - Allows for the viewing of results, providing a multifaceted perspective on the data.

- **PoStLAM – Radiological Analysis Tool :**

- Calculates dose rate interpolation: this functionality uses dose rate values measured at various points to predict the values at unmeasured points.
- Calculates backprojection: this function uses dose rate values to reconstruct the surface distribution of radiation sources from measured data.
- Facilitates the storage of investigations as digital archives, ensuring data preservation.
- Manages data ranging from single components to entire buildings, effectively creating a digital twin.
- Integrates virtual operators (avatars) into the 3D model to assess the accumulated dose of personnel, supporting the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) principle as shown Figure 15.
- Simulates operating scenarios and optimizes workstations for safety and efficiency.

PoStLAM serves as the primary interface for users, enabling comprehensive analysis of both topographical and radiological data. It enhances the point cloud quality and supports topographic studies, point cloud editing, and ALARA studies utilizing the "Avatar" feature. Data processed can be saved and exported for review in Viewer mode by other users, facilitating collaborative analysis and decision-making.

Figure 15: Integration of virtual operators in PoStLAM software for ALARA studies.

To sum up this section, Figure 16 offers a comprehensive visualization of the technological advancements achieved through the CLEANDEM project, encapsulating the progress and innovation.

Figure 16: Overview of the CLEANDEM key technologies.

Together, these technological bricks aim to minimize human exposure to hazardous environments, reduce the time and cost associated with D&D operations, and improve the overall safety and efficiency of the decommissioning process. Through the integration of these advanced technologies, the CLEANDEM project aims to set a new standard in the field of nuclear decommissioning.

Building on the foundation of technological advancements outlined in the CLEANDEM project, the following chapter transitions into exploring case studies and applications, showcasing how these innovations could be practically implemented and the tangible impacts they could have on the field of nuclear decommissioning.

5 Cases Studies and Applications

This chapter will describe the SOGIN (one of the partners in the CLEANDEM project) current approach for site and plant characterization and illustrate the potential of the CLEANDEM solution to address specific operational challenges in different nuclear facilities, from reducing human exposure to radiation to improving the accuracy of radiological mapping.

5.1 SOGIN approach for site and plant characterisation

During the preparation of the final decommissioning plan, the extent and type of radioactive material (irradiated and contaminated structures and components) at the facility shall be determined by means of a detailed characterization survey and based on records collected during the operational period.

In general, the collection of detailed data on the physical, chemical and radiological conditions in a nuclear facility, including activity calculations, in situ measurements and/or sampling and analysis, facilitates a detailed estimation of risk, cost and waste generation during decommissioning, and supports the selection of the overall dismantling strategy – e.g. partial vs. full decontamination, requirements for shielding and for partial removal of equipment and services – and its detailed planning.

It also supports the assessment of different dismantling options and their consequences, including decontamination and dismantling procedures and tools required, and arrangements to ensure the radiological protection of workers, general public and the environment.

The extent and phasing of characterisation will depend on the selected dismantling strategy, with significantly more extensive characterisation being necessary in the case where radioactive substances were handled in free form (radiochemical processes) or without adequate primary containment.

This aspect therefore assumes a relevance of primary importance when it comes to the decommissioning of reprocessing plants. This may require the use of significant resources and, accordingly, result in significant expense being incurred, e.g., relating to the use of knowledgeable and trained personnel, procurement of sampling equipment and instrumentation, laboratory capabilities, simulation/calculation codes, data management systems and record keeping.

SOGIN applies a characterization method recognized as valid by the main international standards, as explained in the next Figure 17.

Figure 17: SOGIN's characterisation scheme.

This approach allows to establish/program very quickly and with a good level of confidence. It includes:

- Operating techniques: decontamination processes, dismantling procedures (hands on, semi remote or fully remote working) and tools required.
- Radiological protection of workers, general public and environment, providing dose assessments, risk assessments, assessment of various scenarios to ensure compliance with the ALARA principle and identify the types of safety and radiological protection required for the protection of workers, general public and environment.
- Waste classification.
- Resulting costs.

In SOGIN a comprehensive characterization programme comprises the following steps:

- Review of historical information.
- Implementation of calculation methods.
- Preparation of the sampling and analysis plan based on an appropriate statistical approach.
- Performance of in situ measurements, sampling, and analyses.
- Review and evaluation of the data obtained, identifying the critical path, where the sequencing of dismantling and demolition activities is important.
- Comparison of calculated results and measured data.

This characterization programme also allows, in particular, to:

- Define equipment and structures removal strategies (e.g., area-based work) that shall be assessed, described, and documented.
- Identify key nuclides (U isotopes, ^{238}Pu , $^{239-240}\text{Pu}$, ^{241}Pu , ^{241}Am , $^{242-244}\text{Cm}$, activation products, etc) or hazardous chemicals, sources of heat or ignition, combustible or flammable materials or other types of hazards that may have been introduced into the structure during the operational phases. This latter information is relevant for the analysis of fire risks.
- Estimate the expected quantities, category and location of radioactive, hazardous, and mixed waste that should be generated during the decommissioning process, which must be described and documented.
- Define any temporary (intermediate) storages of generated or packaged waste, which must also be described and documented. These activities may require additional hazard analysis and controls, as well as special authorizations. Such analyses and authorizations must also be described and documented.
- Define the main work packages on D&D activities, that can be grouped into main groups of activities in the Work Breakdown Structure.

More recently, SOGIN also proceeds to evaluate the possible presence of areas with higher contamination ("hot spots") present within the plant components (e.g., Glove boxes "SaG") using a gamma camera for the investigation as shown in Figure 18. In addition to processing the spread of contamination by viewing it through the colour scales, this instrument provides a dose rate relative to the expected radiation emission.

Figure 18: Gamma camera measurements performed by SOGIN.

The result of the radiological characterisation is also crucial for the design of the auxiliary systems and facilities, such as ventilation and filtration systems, radiation monitoring systems and radioactive waste treatment and conditioning facilities, and for selecting their capacities according to the estimated risks and the identified radioactive wastes streams.

5.2 Suggestions of Applications using The CLEANDEM Solution

The CLEANDEM project presents a transformative approach to D&D operations. Its suite of innovative solutions—ranging from advanced sensing devices and robotic systems to sophisticated digital twins—offers unparalleled potential to enhance safety, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness in nuclear D&D projects. This part describes examples of applications, illustrating how CLEANDEM could be a significant asset across diverse nuclear facilities.

Application 1: Enhancing Safety in a Nuclear Power Plant

A nuclear power plant, with its vast array of possibly contaminated structures and materials, faces significant D&D challenges. Implementing CLEANDEM's robotic system equipped with its advanced sensing technologies could drastically reduce human exposure to hazardous radiation. Robots capable of navigating complex environments autonomously, combined with real-time data monitoring, would ensure that safety remains paramount, showcasing a significant gain in operational safety protocols.

Application 2: Streamlining Operations in a Nuclear Power Plant

CLEANDEM's digital twin technology, integrated with data from various sensors, could offer a dynamic model of the facility and it could be used in optimizing the decommissioning timeline and reducing associated costs.

Application 3: Improving Accuracy in a Nuclear Power Plant

A nuclear power plant could benefit from CLEANDEM's comprehensive data integration capabilities. By fusing topographical and radiological data collected from portable devices, CLEANDEM facilitates accurate mapping of contamination hotspots. This precision in identifying and characterizing radiological threats can significantly improve the decision-making process, improving both safety and effectiveness of decommissioning efforts.

Application 4: Advancing Decommissioning Strategies in a Nuclear Power Plant

CLEANDEM's solutions could offer advanced tools for helping scenario planning and strategy formulation. Indeed, the ability to provide continuous and precise radiological assessments enables the adaptation of decommissioning strategies in real-time. This adaptability not only mitigates potential risks but also ensures that D&D operations proceed with an optimal balance of safety, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

Application 5: Navigating Complexities in Research and Fuel Cycle Facilities

The diverse and intricate nature of those sites, encompassing research and fuel cycle facilities, requires a multifaceted approach to decommissioning. CLEANDEM's technologies, particularly its robotic platform, capable of performing detailed environmental scans, could play a crucial role in safely navigating and mapping these complexities. The integration of digital twin technology could further aid in planning and executing targeted D&D operations, enhancing the overall management and execution of decommissioning tasks.

Table 1 summarizes various challenges for different nuclear facilities and presents the expected outcome using the CLEANDEM solution.

Use Case Scenario	Example of Operational Challenges	Expected Outcome with CLEANDEM
Nuclear Power Plant	Significant D&D challenges due to contaminated structures and materials.	Enhanced safety through reduced human exposure to hazardous radiation via autonomous robotic systems and real-time data monitoring.
	Need to optimize the decommissioning timeline and reduce costs.	Improved operational efficiency and reduced D&D expenses through precise planning and simulation using digital twin technology.
	Requirement for accurate mapping of contamination hotspots.	Enhanced decision-making and safety with precise identification and characterization of radiological threats through comprehensive data integration.
	Developing adaptable decommissioning strategies in real-time.	Advancement in decommissioning strategies, ensuring safety, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness with continuous and precise radiological assessments.
Research and Fuel Cycle Facilities	Navigating decommissioning complexities in a site with diverse facilities.	Improved management and execution of decommissioning tasks through detailed environmental scans and planning with robotic platforms and digital twin technology.

Table 1 : Summary of possible applications of the CLEANDEM Solution.

The CLEANDEM solution offers substantial benefits across various facets of nuclear decommissioning, from enhancing safety and operational efficiency to reducing costs and improving decision-making accuracy. As illustrated through these examples, CLEANDEM's technologies could significantly improve D&D operations at nuclear facilities. Thanks to these innovations, stakeholders have the opportunity to overcome the challenges of nuclear decommissioning with greater confidence, setting new practises for safety, efficiency, and environmental stewardship in the nuclear industry.

6 Conclusion and Future Directions

Key results

CLEANDEM solution represents a technological breakthrough for D&D operations of nuclear sites, employing a UGV platform equipped with a robotic arm and innovative radiological probes. CLEANDEM seeks to support in future the end-user's operations from the initial assessment to the final characterization of the facility. The key results of the project are:

- **Enhanced Safety:** CLEANDEM reduces the need for human intervention and minimizes radiation exposure, establishing safer operational environments. This approach prioritizes the well-being of personnel while maintaining rigorous standards of safety throughout the decommissioning process.
- **Increased Efficiency:** By enabling autonomous acquisition of measurements through robotic technology, CLEANDEM significantly expedites the operational timeline. This efficiency not only accelerates the D&D process but also ensures that critical data is collected swiftly and accurately.
- **Superior Quality:** Through the integration of multiple probes, CLEANDEM enhances the quality and accuracy of measurements. This innovation leads to more reliable data regarding measurement values and precise location tracking in order to build a digital twin.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Embracing low-cost, modular technologies allows CLEANDEM to drastically reduce the financial burden associated with D&D operations. By optimizing the time and resources required, CLEANDEM achieves cost savings that make D&D projects more economically viable and sustainable in the long run.
- **Environmental Stewardship:** CLEANDEM's commitment to minimizing environmental risks underscores efforts to create cleaner D&D operations. By implementing strategies that reduce the ecological footprint, CLEANDEM ensures that environmental impacts are kept at a minimum, reflecting a dedication to sustainability.

These pillars serve as the foundation for CLEANDEM's approach to modernizing decommissioning and dismantling operations.

Future research and development opportunities

The CLEANDEM project has provided a demonstrator to meet the needs and objectives defined by the scenarios selected by the partners. This demonstrator is not the final version as it might be in the future but a more specific version of it.

However, the final objective of this project is not necessarily to produce a single copy intended for a single scenario. This is why the modularity aspect of the solution has been favored as far as possible.

As the final aim will be to develop an industrial-grade version of this platform that can be commercialized and implemented on-site, the project's advancements were designed with this goal in mind, ensuring that the project's innovations can be replicated in an industrial, certified, and durable manner.

The key areas for future developments mainly concern:

- **Robotic Platform and Material Selection:** Choosing a robotic platform and materials that align with industrial requirements for durability and reliability.
- **Communication Protocol Design:** Creating communication protocols that support efficient real-time data transmission and visualization to allow for on-the-spot analysis and decision-making.
- **Standardization of Data:** Data collected and managed within the CLEANDEM framework could be formatted for direct application in waste management and archiving, streamlining subsequent processes and enhancing project efficiency.

7 Complementary Readings

OECD Sources

[1] The Decommissioning and Dismantling of Nuclear Facilities: Status, Approaches, Challenges (2003)

« This report, intended for a broad readership, provides a concise overview of the decommissioning and dismantling of nuclear facilities and associated issues in NEA Member countries. It draws upon a database of fact sheets produced to a standard format by individual Member countries that is accessible online from the NEA website. »

<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264184886-en>

[2] Guide for International Peer Reviews of Decommissioning Cost Studies for Nuclear Facilities (2015)

« The NEA Radioactive Waste Management Committee's Working Party on Decommissioning and Dismantling (WPDD) developed the present guide as a framework for decommissioning cost reviewers and reviewees to prepare for and conduct international peer reviews of decommissioning cost estimate studies for nuclear facilities. It includes checklists that will help national programmes or relevant organisations to assess and improve decommissioning cost estimate practices in the future. This guide will act as the NEA reference for conducting such international peer reviews. »

<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264229907-en>

[3] R&D and Innovation Needs for Decommissioning Nuclear Facilities (2014)

« Nuclear decommissioning activities can greatly benefit from research and development (R&D) projects. This report examines applicable emergent technologies, current research efforts and innovation needs to build a base of knowledge regarding the status of decommissioning technology and R&D. This base knowledge can be used to obtain consensus on future R&D that is worth funding. It can also assist in deciding how to collaborate and optimise the limited pool of financial resources available among NEA member countries for nuclear decommissioning R&D.»

<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264222199-en>

[4] Preparing for Decommissioning During Operation and After Final Shutdown (2018)

« The transition from an operating nuclear facility to the decommissioning phase is critical in the life cycle of every facility. A number of organisational and technical modifications are needed in order for the facility to meet new objectives and requirements, and a certain number of activities must be initiated to support the transition and preparation for the dismantling of the facility. Thorough preparation and planning is key for the success of global decommissioning and dismantling projects, both to minimise delays and undue costs and to ensure a safe and efficient decommissioning process. The aim of this report is to inform regulatory bodies, policy makers and planners about the relevant aspects and activities that should begin during the last years of operation and following the end of operation. Compiling lessons learnt from experiences and good practices in NEA member countries, the report supports the further optimisation of transition strategies, activities and measures that will ensure adequate preparation for decommissioning and dismantling. »

<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264303126-en>

[5] Selecting Strategies for the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities (2006)

«This status report on Selecting Strategies for the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities is based on the viewpoints and materials presented at a seminar held in Tarragona, Spain on 1-4 September 2003 as well as the experience of the NEA Working Party on Decommissioning and Dismantling (WPDD). It identifies, reviews and analyses factors influencing decommissioning strategies and addresses the challenges associated with balancing these factors in the process of strategy selection. It gives recognition to the fact that, in addition to technical characteristics, there are many other factors that influence the selection of a decommissioning strategy and that cannot be quantified, such as policy, regulatory and socio-economic factors and aspects that reach far into the future. Uncertainties associated with such factors are a challenge to those who have to take decisions on a decommissioning strategy. »

[Selecting Strategies for the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities: A Status Report \(oecd-nea.org\)](https://www.oecd-nea.org)

IAEA Sources

[6] Selection of Decommissioning Strategies: Issues and Factors (2005)

«When selecting a proper decommissioning strategy in a specific facility, a range of general and site-specific factors needs to be considered. These factors include cost, health, and safety issues and environmental (HSE) impact, availability of resources, stakeholder involvement, etc. In some cases, the lack of a single key resource could result in the elimination of some decommissioning strategies. Good practice may not always be achieved in Member States due to constraints or overruling factors such as a lack of funds or a lack of waste management infrastructure. Constraints or overruling factors are often attributable to inadequate decommissioning planning. This in turn may be due to inadequate legal and regulatory frameworks. Some relevant constraints and conditions have been evaluated. The objective of the evaluation is to identify key issues and to provide recommendations to Member States in which these constraints and factors prevail, to promote actions in support of good decommissioning practice. »

[IAEA-TECDOC-1478](https://www.iaea.org/publications/tecdoc/tecdoc1478)

European Commission Sources

[7] Study on the market for decommissioning nuclear facilities in the European Union (2019)

«The European decommissioning and dismantling (D&D) market of nuclear facilities is featured by a significant long-term growth, hence representing an important opportunity of businesses and employment creation in the continent. In the next 20 years, the market size of the D&D market for nuclear power plants may reach EUR 2.2 billion per year, with an expected decline of the D&D expenses in the United Kingdom balanced by the progressive growth of the German programme (following the decision to phase-out from nuclear). The completion of this latter will then be balanced by the consolidation of the French programme, which may drive the market to a peak of about EUR 3.0 billion per year in 2045 (but depending on decisions on long term operations of existing nuclear power plants). Despite the positive outlook, a number of challenges exist to enable an open, safe and fast-growing D&D market in the EU. First, specific issues linked to key schedule and cost drivers of the D&D projects (e.g., national waste strategies, national regulations, social impact of installations shutdowns) may induce potential investors to perceive the market still as

uncertain and highly complex and hence discourage investments. Second, the D&D industrial landscape remains largely domestic in several Member States and with a predominant role and budget share for the utilities/operators/owners' own personnel, resulting in somewhat reduced competition. Third, unlike D&D of nuclear power plants (which relies upon proven processes and technologies), D&D for fuel cycle and research installations still requires a certain degree of industrial development before being considered as a completely mastered activity. »

[Study on market for decommissioning nuclear facilities in the European Union - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

